

Blue-Cloud

Piloting innovative services for Marine Research & the Blue Economy

Blue-Cloud D3.5. Pilot Demonstrators Principal Results, Achievements & Actionable Items for the Future Report

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Glossary

Acronym	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
BPNS	Belgium part of the North Sea
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service
DDAS	Data Discovery & Access Service
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
GRSF	Global record of Stocks and Fisheries
KEGG	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
MEI	Marine Environment Indication
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NPZ	Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton
PAR	photosynthetically available radiation
PFT	Phytoplankton Functional Types
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SSI	Storm severity index
VLab	Virtual Laboratory
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Executive summary

Blue-Cloud has achieved significant results since the start of the project in October 2019. Blue-Cloud working environments have been used by more than 1,300 users in total spread across 20 countries. 15 services released by Blue-Cloud are now available in the EOSC marketplace and 12 of them have been developed in the framework of **5 Pilot scientific demonstrators** and are at the core of this deliverable. Up to mid of September 2022, more than 25,700 working sessions have been executed, with an average of 1,286 working sessions per month and an average of 55 working analytics sessions executed every month by the users of the VLabs.

This document describes in details the 5 pilot demonstrators and the 12 services developed during the Blue Cloud project as part of the Blue-Cloud thematic Virtual Labs. For each service, the main scientific and technical outputs are highlighted. All together these services showcase the great potential and opportunities offered by cloud and Virtual Research Environment (VRE) technologies when combined with open science. These services and the Blue Cloud framework, consisting of a Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service and a well-equipped Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment, are prototypes and forerunners of enhanced and future services using state-of-the art IT technology (cloud, VRE, data and services federation, big data). Increasingly, these are becoming strategic for the future of operational marine services and the digital twin of the ocean.

1 Introduction

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE)¹, based upon the D4Science e-infrastructure as developed and managed by CNR-ISTI, facilitates collaborative research, using a variety of data sets and analytical tools, complemented by generic services such as sub-setting, pre-processing, harmonizing, publishing and visualization. The D4Science e-infrastructure also has proven solutions for connecting to external computing platforms and means for orchestrating distributed services, which are instrumental for smart connections to other e-infrastructures in the Blue-Cloud system.

Within the Blue-Cloud pilot project, 5 Virtual Labs have been developed and deployed making use of the analytical tools and generic services as provided through the Blue-Cloud VRE, and the data repositories as made accessible through the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service² and through external data services³. The Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs considered real-life demonstrators for web based open science and are open and available for testing by different research communities. Each Virtual Lab comprises a series of applications for data processing, publishing data results and managing computation routines as well as services for collaboration, providing open science-friendly working environments for its users to analyse datasets and (re)generate research products.

This document provides an overview of the different services developed as part of the Blue-Cloud thematic demonstrators. In this context the document describes the following 12 services:

Demonstrator #1

1. **Zooplankton essential ocean variable.** The service provides a methodology (using DIVAnd) to generate zooplankton gridded abundance maps, based on *in situ* observations of the six most abundant Copepods species in the North East Atlantic for a 72-year period.
2. **Phytoplankton essential ocean variable.** The service provides a methodology (using Artificial Intelligence (AI)) to generate global open ocean 3D gridded products of chlorophyll-a, proxy of the total phytoplankton biomass and indicators of phytoplankton diversity.
3. **Modelling phyto&zoo plankton interactions.** The service provides a workflow to run a mechanistic Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton (NPZ) model using near real-time data to quantify the relative contributions of the bottom-up and top-down drivers in phytoplankton dynamics

Demonstrator #2

4. **Plankton genomics.** The first part of the service is to enable the discovery of unknown genes using the large dataset collected during the Tara Oceans Expedition. The output file is used for the second part of the service where the influence of the environmental context on planktonic organisms in a given geographical area is examined using a machine learning regression method.

¹ <https://blue-cloud.d4science.org/web/blue-cloudlab>

² <https://data.blue-cloud.org/>

³ <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures>

Demonstrator #3

5. **Marine environment indicator (MEI) generator.** The prototype MEI Generator service is a web graphical interface that allows the user to generate and display value-added environmental data from generic marine data.
6. **The ocean patterns and ocean regimes indicators are based on machine learning approaches.** They consist in applying an unsupervised clustering, using a probabilistic model, to a set of profiles (patterns) or time-series (regimes) from a structured or an unstructured dataset for any physical or chemical data.
7. **Storm severity index.** The service calculates maps and time series of exceptional atmospheric wind or storm circumstances that can affect sea circulations and coastal regions such as the Mediterranean Sea.
8. **Simple access to carbon data.** This technical service provides information on how to search and retrieve subsets of inorganic carbon data without having to download the full files by using a data server largely used by the oceanographic community.

Demonstrator #4

9. **Fisheries atlas.** The service delivers an online fisheries atlas of EU waters and beyond, providing harmonised time-series of catch, commodities and trade data.
10. **Global record of stocks and fisheries.** The objective of the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) is to deliver a scalable and robust open data portal for fisheries data in EU waters and beyond, with a focus on assessment status and management of natural living resources.

Demonstrator #5

11. **Aquaculture cage detection.** The combined use of Earth Observation (EO) images (Sentinel 1) and GIS (Geographic Information Systems) is a mature practice for the global management of aquaculture.
12. **Coastal pond detection and land classification.** The service has been developed to distinguish between permanent ponds and season rice-fields (sawah) in southern Sulawesi using Sentinel 2 images and an AI random forest approach.

The following sections report the key outcomes of the services developed, highlighting the importance of providing data, methodologies and data products that can be used by the blue community.

2 Demonstrator # 1 – Zoo- and Phytoplankton Essential Ocean Variable products

Phyto- and zooplankton diversity and biomass are recognized as Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) (Miloslavich et al., 2018) with the objective to implement conservation and management actions. Plankton is also used as indicators for the health of the pelagic habitats. Data products about plankton feeds directly into policies, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD); where pelagic habitats are considered a priority below descriptor 1 (Biodiversity) and plankton is considered vital for the functioning of marine food webs (descriptor 4). The **Zoo- and Phytoplankton EOV demonstrator**⁴ provides a description of the current state of the plankton communities and forecasts their evolution, representing valuable information for the modelling, assessment and management of the pelagic ecosystems.

Currently there are 136 users registered to the VLab, developers being the most active at the moment. Additional users are envisioned to benefit from the workflows provided, that can be easily reproduced with other data, to elucidate key plankton research questions at a larger spatio-temporal resolution. Furthermore, this VLab will provide the basis for further development in the next phase of the Blue-Cloud project.

2.1 Zooplankton essential ocean variable (EOVs)

2.1.1 Short description of the service

Zooplankton are an integral part of the pelagic food web, playing an important role as (1) grazers of phytoplankton, (2) providing food to higher trophic levels and (3) producing faecal pellets to the carbon flux. It is expected that certain species of zooplankton will shift their distributions in response to climate change, having important consequences in all the components of the food web. The objective of the zooplankton EOV demonstrator is to assess the current and future state of zooplankton communities. To do this, data from the Continuous Plankton Recorder (CPR) was used. The CPR survey is the most standardised and spatio-temporal extensive monitoring program about plankton. CPR data in combination with modelling techniques such as neural networks help to investigate long-term trends and seasonal patterns of zooplankton communities and their relation with key environmental variables.

The zooplankton EOV demonstrator provides a methodology to generate zooplankton gridded abundance maps, based on *in situ* observations of the six most abundant Copepods species in the North East Atlantic for a 72-year period. The workflow uses the DIVAnd software tool (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) to create interpolated maps. DIVAnd has been designed to interpolate sparse, *in situ* measurements onto a regular grid in an optimal way,

⁴ See <https://blue-cloud.org/vlabs/zoo-and-phytoplankton-eov-products>. A factsheet is also available on Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7229886>

considering constraints such as the presence of obstacles (coastlines, islands) or currents (Barth et al., 2014). DIVAnd is used together with a Neural Network (Multilayer perceptron) to improve the interpolation and it shows the probability of the occurrence of a certain species based on environmental data, as co-variables.

2.1.2 Principal scientific results

The input data consists of zooplankton abundance data from 366 379 CPR samples acquired between 1946 and 2017 in the Northeast Atlantic Ocean (90°W-40°E and 40-30°N). The Jupyter notebooks generate maps in netCDF-4 format for six copepod species: *Calanus finmarchicus*, *Calanus helgolandicus*, *Temora longicornis*, *Metridia lucens*, *Acartia sp.* And *Oithona sp.* The last two were combined to genus level to improve the representativeness of the sample size. CPR data were log transformed using $[\log(n + 1)]$ in order to homogenise the variance. The first Jupyter notebook provided, prepares the covariables, splits data into training and validation datasets and performs the interpolation and neural network. The co-variables used in the neural network are temperature, salinity, nitrate, silicate, phosphate concentrations, distance from coast and bathymetry. The second Jupyter notebook allows users to visualise the results. This consists of gridded abundance maps generated after performing the DIVAnd analysis. As an example (Figure 1), the interpolation of *Acartia sp.* And *Oithona sp.* In the Northeast Atlantic between 1946 and 2017 can be observed. The plots on the left represent *in situ* data and on the right the gridded field after the interpolation. The scale represents log-transformed abundance. The blank areas on the left map are regions with no observations, hence where the expected error is very high. The error field obtained along with the interpolated field allows showing the gridded results where the confidence is high (near the observations) but full fields are available.

Figure 1 Gridded abundance map of *Metridia lucens* in the Northeast Atlantic in 2004 and 2013. The plots on the left represent *in situ* data, and on the right the analyses performed with DIVAnd. The scale represents log-transformed abundance.

To investigate species distribution over time, it is also possible to perform the analysis per year, with a temporal correlation (i.e., the gridded field for a given year is influenced by observations acquired in other years). However, due to changes in sampling effort per year, it is difficult to disentangle these from changes in species distribution. Figure 2 shows the analyses for *Metridia lucens*, where you can observe the increase over time particularly visible at the west of Ireland. The strong increase was consistent over several years in the analysis and in the binned observations. The binned observation represents the average of the reported value for the corresponding grid cell and year.

Figure 2 Gridded abundance map of *Metridia lucens* in the Northeast Atlantic in 2004 and 2013. The plots on the left represent *in situ* data, and on the right the analyses performed with DIVAnd. The scale represents log-transformed abundance.

2.2 Phytoplankton essential ocean variables (EOVs)

2.2.1 Short description of the service

Phytoplankton is key to several scientific and socio-economic questions. For example, its biomass and composition affects critical processes in the oceans, in particular the capacity to sequester carbon and the flow of carbon energy through the marine food webs. Therefore, developing a global 3D (three-dimensional) view of the biomass and composition of phytoplankton assemblages in the oceans is critical to reduce uncertainties regarding the status of marine ecosystems and to improve the ability to predict the evolution of pelagic ecosystems under climate change scenarios. In recent years, the Biogeochemical-Argo (BGC-Argo) global observation network has largely expanded and now provides the *in situ* data required for training and validating a new generation of machine

learning-based algorithms, which are essential for obtaining a global 3D view of biogeochemical data in the ocean.

The phytoplankton EOVS demonstrator aims to provide a methodology to generate global open ocean 3D gridded products of chlorophyll a (Chla) concentration which is a proxy of the total phytoplankton biomass and of Phytoplankton Functional Types (PFT) expressed in terms of Chla associated with 3 main phytoplankton groups (i.e. pico-, nano- and microphytoplankton) which are indicators of phytoplankton diversity.

The proposed machine learning method follows the SOCA algorithm developed by Sauzède et al. (2016), which is based on an artificial neural network, specifically a Multi-Layer Perceptron, MLP. Two different MLP-based algorithms are developed. The first MLP retrieves the depth-resolved Chla product and it is trained using *in situ* depth-resolved measurements of Chla, temperature and salinity (T/S). The retrieval of the depth-resolved PFT product relies itself on two distinct MLP-based algorithms, the first one is trained using a database of phytoplankton pigments determined by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC), chlorophyll fluorescence and T/S profiles and the second one is trained using the “PFT-enriched” considering *in situ* and satellite data.

2.2.2 Principal scientific results

Approximately 28.000 matchups of satellite (Remote Sensing Reflectance, Photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) and Sea Level Anomaly) to BGC-Argo Chla, T/S and PFT data were used, from which the 80% were randomly extracted for the training of the algorithm while the remaining 20% were used for the validation.

The validation of the model was performed considering the determination coefficient (r^2) and the slope of the linear regression (Figure 3a) between the Chla concentration derived from the algorithm (y-axis) and the Chla concentration measured *in situ* by the floats (x-axis). Then the model error is estimated using the Median Absolute Percent Difference (MAPD, %). The linear regression comparison between predicted and measured data shows satisfactory results with $r^2=0.8$, slope value of 0.92 and a relatively low global error (MAPD=28%). Similarly, the algorithm performed well for the PFT product (Figure 3b) with a good representation of the three phytoplankton size groups over the biomass gradient and a relatively low mean error (18-29%).

Figure 3 Density scatterplots for the validation of the model. (3a) Chla biomass and (3b) PTF-specific Chla derived from the algorithm (y-axes) against Chla biomass and Chla PTF measured in situ (x-axes).

The Jupyter notebooks retrieve monthly fields for the year 2018 at 15 depths (0-1000 m) for Chla biomass and diversity. As an example, Figure 4 shows the 2 products in winter (left plots) and summer (right plots) at surface for Chla biomass (4a) and PFT-specific Chla product (4b). One can observe the typical phytoplankton austral summer bloom in the Southern Ocean (left plots), compared to the less pronounced phytoplankton summer bloom in the Northern latitudes (right plots).

Figure 4 3D Global maps of Chla biomass (4a) and Chla for the three size groups (pico-, nano- and microphytoplankton); and (4b), for the year 2018 in January (left plots) and June (right plots) at 0m depth.

To observe the seasonal and vertical variability, a cross section of the PFT-specific Chla product in the Western Mediterranean Sea (Figure 5) was extracted from the global product. One can observe an increase of the Chla biomass in the surface layer of the ocean during the typical spring bloom. This feature is followed by a decrease in the Chla biomass in the upper layer and the occurrence of a deep Chla maximum in summer due to the stratified oligotrophic conditions. The phytoplankton assemblage appears dominated in spring by micro- as well as nanophytoplankton. In contrast, smaller picophytoplankton and nanophytoplankton make the largest contribution to the biomass during the summer season.

Figure 5 Cross section in the Western Mediterranean Sea of the Chla attributed to the micro-, nano- and picophytoplankton (from left to right)

2.3 Modelling phyto & zoo –plankton interactions

2.3.1 Short description of the service

This service provides a workflow to run a mechanistic Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton (NPZ) model using near real-time data to quantify the relative contributions of the bottom-up and top-down drivers in phytoplankton dynamics.

The NPZ model as presented in Everaert et al. (2015) was used to disentangle the monthly, seasonal and yearly variations in phytoplankton biomass dynamics in the Belgian Part of the North Sea (BPNS) for the period 2014-2017. Monthly observations of nutrients, solar irradiance, sea surface temperature, chlorophyll-a and zooplankton biomass from 2011- 2014 were used as input data for the model to quantify how the relative importance of these determinants changed along a near-offshore gradient. The spatial regions comprised in total 9 locations distributed in the nearshore region (< 10 km to the coastline), midshore region (10 – 30 km), and offshore region (> 30 km).

The validation of the model is performed by comparing the model predictions, i.e. phyto- and zooplankton biomass, with field observations. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) is calculated between prediction values and observational values.

2.3.2 Principal scientific results

Phytoplankton biomass dynamics (expressed in Chlorophyll-a) followed a general seasonal cycle as in other temperate regional seas, with a distinct spring bloom and a modest autumn bloom. This is remarkable in the BPNS, because autumn blooms were not present in this area before (Nohe et al., 2020), indicating that the North Sea switched back to a classic bimodal bloom pattern. This was also observed in Flowcam data for 2017 and later.

Zooplankton increased in response to the spring and autumn phytoplankton blooms, with a time lag between the peak in phytoplankton density and zooplankton density, as theoretically expected from a classic predator-prey pattern (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Phyto- (solid line) and zooplankton (dashed line) density simulations using the nutrient– phytoplankton–zooplankton model in a region of the BPNS. The lines represent the average phyto- and zooplankton density predictions.

The relative contribution of factors determining phytoplankton biomass dynamics varied spatially and temporally (Figure 7). Throughout a calendar year, solar irradiance and zooplankton grazing were the most influential determinants in all regions, i.e. explained 38% – 65% of the variation in the offshore region, 45% – 71% in the midshore region, and 56% – 77% in the nearshore region. In the near and midshore regions, nutrients are most limiting the phytoplankton production in the month following the spring bloom (44%– 55%). Nutrients are a determinant throughout the year in the offshore region (27% – 62%). During winter, sea surface temperature is a determinant in all regions (15% – 17%).

Figure 7 Monthly averaged relative contributions for each determinant of phytoplankton biomass dynamics for the three regions, i.e. nearshore, midshore and offshore. The shaded areas indicate the 95% confidence interval. Potential determinants are Dissolved Inorganic Nitrogen (DIN), Phosphate (PO4), Silicate (SiO4), Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR), Sea Surface Temperature (SST), and zooplankton grazing.

2.4 Blue-Cloud added value

Blue-Cloud VRE services were crucial for the development of this demonstrator. For example, the high cost of heavy computations in an ordinary machine was not a limitation to develop the products. By using parallel computing, the computation of some algorithms was reduced from hours to minutes. The high number of cores and RAM available were very useful for the storage of heavy datasets. This demonstrator also played an important role in shaping the VRE. As the demonstrator evolved over time, more functionalities were needed and implemented by D4Science to support the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Following the FAIR principles as the basis of Blue-Cloud, the demonstrator was developed using open data. For example, thanks to the open data policy and the effort of MBA to make CPR data open and available through EMODnet Biology, this data could be used to generate the Zooplankton EOVs product. Furthermore, due to the complexity of the functions contained in the Jupyter notebooks and R markdown, an open science framework such as Blue-Cloud enables non programming experts to reuse and reproduce the methods. Users are therefore stimulated to extend and build further on the data products.

Blue-Cloud brings together different Blue Data Infrastructures (BDI) enabling the interaction between the infrastructures and across the scientists of the demonstrators. This demonstrator builds further on existing efforts and has been extended to other data platforms as a way to increase the impact and user-uptake of the demonstrator. For example, the Phytoplankton EOVs are offered as a product in Copernicus Marine catalogue and it is being explored to showcase the Zooplankton EOVs in the upcoming EMODnet central portal.

Thanks to Blue-Cloud, the demonstrator has gained interest in mayor EU Biodiversity initiatives. For example, the demonstrator products were added to the metadata file on relevant variables and GES indicators for D1C6, in the framework of the second workshop on the MSFD pelagic habitats organised by the Join Research Centre from the EU.

2.5 References

Barth, A., Beckers, J.-M., Troupin, C., Alvera-Azcárate, A., and Vandenbulcke, L.: DIVAnd-1.0: n-dimensional variational data analysis for ocean observations, *Geosci. Model Dev.*, 7, 225–241, doi:<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-7-225-2014>, 2014.

Everaert, G., De Laender, F., Goethals, P. L. M. and Janssen, C. R.: Relative contribution of persistent organic pollutants to marine phytoplankton biomass dynamics in the North Sea and the Kattegat, *Chemosphere*, 134, 76–83,660 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.03.084>, 2015.

Miloslavich, P., Bax, N.J., Simmons, S.E., Klein, E., Appeltans, W., Aburto-Oropeza, O., Andersen Garcia, M., Batten, S.D., Benedetti-Cecchi, L., Checkley Jr, D.M. and Chiba, S.. Essential ocean variables for global sustained observations of biodiversity and ecosystem changes. *Global Change Biology*, 24(6), pp.2416-2433, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14108>, 2018.

Nohe, A., Goffin, A., Tyberghein, L., Lagring, R., De Cauwer, K., Vyverman, W. and Sabbe, K.: Marked changes in diatom and dinoflagellate biomass, composition and seasonality in the Belgian Part of the North Sea between the 1970s and 2000s, *Sci. Total Environ.*, 716, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.136316>, 2020.

Sauzède, R., Hervé Claustre, J. Uitz, C. Jamet, G. Dall’Olmo, F. d’Ortenzio, B. Gentili, A. Poteau, and C. Schmechtig. “A neural network-based method for merging ocean color and Argo data to extend surface bio-optical properties to depth: Retrieval of the particulate backscattering coefficient.” *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 121, no. 4 (2016): 2552-2571. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JC011408>, 2016.

3 Demonstrator # 2 – Plankton Genomics

The approach to model several gene clusters together, implemented in the Plankton Genomics demonstrator, is novel and is thought to be the only correct way to extrapolate genomic information because it gives information of relative, rather than absolute, abundance of the targets. As for any other demonstrator, the fact that it is easy to run from the Vlab gives it additional value.

There are around 50 registered users on the Vlab, mainly members of the Blue-Cloud consortium. The Vlab has a great potential for further exploitation considering the work that the scientific genomic community is currently doing to further develop, build and organise its measurements to be able to do additional research and measurements in the future.

3.1 Short description of the service

The service enables the discovery of unknown genes using the large dataset collected during the Tara Oceans Expedition. The service allows retrieving unknown genes from annotation files for 4 different plankton size classes and then building gene clusters by similarities of sequences and larger metabolic pathways.

The output file is used for the second functionality of the service of this demonstrator where the influence of the environmental context on planktonic organisms and by extension on the composition and genetic potential of plankton, in a given geographical area is examined. This notebook uses a machine learning regression method, namely multivariate gradient boosting (i.e. several gene clusters related to the same metabolic pathway are modelled at once).

3.2 Principal scientific results

3.2.1 Context and rationale of the study

Picoeukaryotes, marine eukaryotic unicellular organisms, are one of the most diverse and abundant group of organisms in the sunlit layer of the world's oceans. They are involved in a large diversity of metabolic pathways, including carbon and nitrogen biogeochemical cycles. Intensive environmental genomic sampling (e.g., Tara Oceans) revealed the hidden taxonomic and functional diversity of picoeukaryotes. However, the biogeographical distribution of this functional diversity remains an active research field. Recent advances in metagenomic data processing (e.g., metagenome assembled genomes; MAGs) provided a new tool for semi-quantitative study of picoeukaryotes. Because picoeukaryotic MAGs and their associated functions are defined as genome-based taxonomic units, one can theoretically derive their biogeography from their response to environmental conditions (i.e., habitat modelling). In this context, this demonstrator provides the first comprehensible and highly replicable framework to derive functional biogeography from metagenomic-based relative abundances.

3.2.2 Methodological overview

The habitat modelling framework is based on metagenomic relative abundances (i.e., derived from the MAG data) and the corresponding environmental conditions (i.e., derived from climatologies) at each Tara Oceans sampling station. The metagenomic relative abundances correspond to the number of MAG reads, grouped by cluster of genes of similar sequences (i.e., hereafter “connected components”). From this dataset, the framework selected connected components that are markers of a user-defined metabolic pathway of interest, using KEGG Orthology annotations (<https://www.genome.jp/kegg/>). Based on relative abundance pattern similarities across Tara Oceans stations, the machine learning framework (i.e., multivariate boosted tree regressors; MBTR) computes the multivariate response of connected components to environmental variables. Using the computed environmental responses, the distributional pattern of each connected component across world oceans was then projected. Because connected components (i.e., and the MAGs therein) are functionally and taxonomically annotated, the projections can be aggregated by enzymes or taxonomic classes of interest.

3.2.3 Results and discussion

Here, the results related to C4-carbon concentration mechanism (C4-CCM) in picoeukaryotes are presented, a metabolic pathway aiming to increase the carbon fixation rate of RUBISCO, the baseline photosynthetic enzyme (Figure 8). The outputs are divided between potential and realized distributional patterns, respectively corresponding to outputs (i) where the taxonomical effect was alleviated and (ii) where the taxonomical dominance was included in the projections. First, potential distributional patterns of C4-CCM present high correlations between enzymes (Figure 8A, top correlogram). Their potential distributional pattern presents a high intensity peak towards tropical latitudes (Figure 8B, top plots), suggesting affinity towards warm, oligotrophic water conditions. In other words, these results highlight an important functional redundancy between C4-CCM enzymes in tropical waters. In contrast, realized distributional patterns – that includes information on the taxonomic dominance in the observed data – present lower correlations, especially RUBISCO (Figure 8A, bottom correlogram). Their projected distributional patterns highlight divergences between RUBISCO and C4-enzymes, with respective intensity peaks in temperate and tropical waters (Figure 8B, bottom plots). Moreover, the PEPDK enzyme, associated to a specific metabolic subtype, is largely dominant in polar waters (Figure 8B, bottom plot). By analyzing the taxonomic composition of MAGs characterized by a polar distributional pattern, this specificity of PEPCK was related to the important dominance of Prymnesiophyceae (Figure 8C).

Figure 8 Available outputs for the potential and realized distributional patterns with (A) correlograms between distributional patterns, (B) projected distributional patterns and (C) taxonomic composition related to different pattern types.

The important affinity of C4-CCM enzymes towards tropical oligotrophic waters may reflect the efficiency of picoeukaryotes in these environments (i.e., high surface to cytoplasm ratio; efficient nutrient uptakes). In addition, C4-CCM requires additional ATP generation to increase the RUBISCO efficiency, with MDC-enzymes (+2 ATP) or PEPCK (+1 ATP). Thus, at low irradiance, the gain from MDC-enzymes pathway in minimizing photorespiration is largely alleviated by the extra energy cost. In contrast, PEPCK is more efficient at low-irradiance environments (e.g., polar latitudes).

3.3 Blue Cloud added value

Because of its multiple and interdisciplinary data sources and heavy computing cost, the Blue-Cloud infrastructure is perfectly suited for this work. Moreover, due to the diversity of metabolic pathways contained in the metagenomic data, an open science framework such as Blue-Cloud, will allow researchers, students, and academics to explore this data further, for a better understanding of planktonic functional diversity across oceans.

4 Demonstrator # 3 – Marine Environmental Indicators

The service provides scientific indicators for end users such as environmental protection agencies and international stakeholders in MSFD, UN SDG 14, UN SDG 13 and Blue Economy. This VLab will be further developed as part of the new Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

There are around 170 registered users on the VLab. The growth of the userbase is linked to the fact that the prototype built as part of Blue-Cloud needs to be enhanced with additional data (planned in Blue-Cloud 2026).

4.1 Marine Environment Indication (MEI) generator

4.1.1 Short description of the service

The prototype MEI Generator service is a web graphical interface that allows the user to generate and display value-added environmental data from generic marine data.

These value-added environmental data can be an average over time, ocean patterns or regimes, depending on the method chosen by the user; the output is proposed as a time series or a map.

The current prototype and the one described here, uses Copernicus Marine products (physical modelling products from the Mediterranean Sea) as input data. The method implemented allows various averages.

4.1.2 Principal scientific results

The development of this service highlights the importance of consolidating and promoting the practice for implementing interoperable solutions. It offers a web user interface for the exploitation of multiple data sources with multiple algorithms

The current implementation is already based on a distributed architecture where data sources and algorithms can be located on different internet sites (i.e. different Research Infrastructures). The interface tool has a harmonised knowledge of both the data sources and algorithms, and based on that, allows the implementation of new processing workflows, specifying the exact input dataset (usually the subset of a marine product), the algorithm and the desired parameters. With the use of this knowledge, the interface has the flexibility to offer all and only the correct combinations of inputs and algorithms.

From the perspective of the algorithms, the improvement is intended to be the transparent and harmonised access to data sources which are offered from different Marine Data Infrastructures with different access protocols.

The implementation choices of this service are showing the positive impact of software modules dedicated to manage the interoperability issues of datasets, and then the interoperability issues of

algorithms. In this way, especially the Data Infrastructures are not initially impacted by additional requirements, while the final user of the service can reach the maximum benefit, because ideally the access and exploitation of any research product or algorithm is possible in a seamless way. The baseline for the implementation of this kind of software module are the definition of a generalised data access API and the definition of a Interface Definition Language (IDL) for the access/execution of algorithms. During the project these specifications were consolidated, and as a result, any implementation of algorithm that is compliant with the IDL, can be executed from the interface tool, all the data sources that are using an access method implemented inside the software module, can be exploited through the generalised data access API.

Figure 9 Example of working flow for the MEI generator

4.1.3 Blue Cloud added value

The Blue-Cloud project is facilitating the co-design of infrastructure features (new or innovative) which are actually fit for purpose to address some important societal needs, for instance related to the UN Ocean Decade.

This step is important because it implies collaboration among stakeholders that are focused on different aspects, for instance more related to addressing a scientific challenge, or more related to developing research infrastructures.

In this way, on one hand, the scientific investigation will rely on effective infrastructure, while on the other hand, the infrastructure will rely on applications that are actually related to societal needs.

The awareness of the importance of this step, is a pre-condition for preparing the ground for the scientific investigation related to the future challenges.

4.2 Ocean pattern & regime indicators

4.2.1 Short description of the service

The Ocean Patterns and Ocean Regimes indicators are based on machine learning approaches. They consist in applying an unsupervised clustering, or classification method called GMM (Gaussian Mixture Model), a probabilistic model, to a set of profiles (patterns) or time-series (regimes), from a structured (model output, reanalysis) or an unstructured (set of observations) dataset. Any type of variable can be used: temperature, salinity, etc ... The data profiles or time-series are automatically gathered into several clusters, or classes, depending on their vertical or temporal structure. When analysing the different clusters, spatial or temporal coherences can be revealed, which are defined as the Ocean Patterns and Ocean Regimes indicators.

The service offers users a flexible and innovative approach to perform statistical analyses on ocean dataset.

4.2.2 Principal scientific results

4.2.2.A *Method and workflow*

The core method behind those two indicators is the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM). This clustering method decomposes the probability density functions (PDF) of the dataset into a sum of gaussian PDF. Users should only choose the number of classes. In the input, there is no spatial or temporal information so the classes depend only on the PDF of the dataset: the vertical structure similarities in the case of profiles (Ocean Patterns) and seasonal structure similarities in the case of time series (Ocean Regimes).

These indicators, using Artificial Intelligence techniques, have been developed into Jupyter Notebooks available to users in the Marine Environmental Indicators Virtual Lab. The workflow is structured into two notebooks for both indicators, a model development notebook, and a prediction notebook (figure 10).

Figure 10 Workflow of the proposed ocean pattern & regime indicator services

In the model development notebook, users can design a clustering model: they can choose the number of classes to apply, then the model is trained (fitted) with the training dataset. Some plots are available to adjust the optimal number of classes. Finally, the trained model is saved into a file, so that it can be used in the prediction method. In the prediction notebook, a trained model is applied to some data, so that the profiles or time series from the input data selection will be sorted into clusters. Then different plots are proposed to analyse the results: spatial and temporal distributions, and median time series or profiles for each class.

4.2.2.B Examples

For the Ocean Patterns Indicator, here (figure 11) is an example dataset of temperature profiles in the Mediterranean Sea (from GLOBAL_REANALYSIS_PHY_001_030 CMEMS product, downloaded inside the jupyter notebooks). Vertical profiles are classified into 8 classes. In general, one class is predominant in all Mediterranean Sea for each month: the classification shows the evolution of temperature profiles through one year: from mixture profiles in winter to more stratified ones in summer.

Figure 11 Example of ocean pattern indicators (vertical profiles) in the Mediterranean Sea during year 2018

4.2.3 Blue Cloud added value

Within the demonstrator #3 "Marine Environmental Indicators", the methods Ocean Patterns and Ocean Regimes Indicators, based on machine learning approaches, offer new types of statistical perspective when analysing ocean data. The Blue Cloud environment makes those new approaches effectively available to a wider audience of end-users. Blue Cloud most important added value for those indicators are:

- Efficient access to datasets from various providers (<https://data.blue-cloud.org>)
- On-demand Jupyter notebooks with python environments compatible with latest development in earth data science (Pangeo)
- Computing infrastructure allowing us to embedded our method within a friendly user interface (MEI Generator)

Furthermore, to foster the establishment of the FAIR principles, special attention is dedicated to the assessment of all the most relevant aspects to ensure not only the findability of the generated data and of the method itself, but also the interoperability with the many data infrastructures that could potentially provide valuable input data to this method.

4.3 Storm severity index

4.3.1 Short description of the service

The Storm Severity Index (SSI) service calculates maps and time series of exceptional atmospheric wind or storm circumstances that can impact sea circulations and coastal regions such as the Mediterranean Sea.

The SSI service can be used to study individual storms (Event SSI, ESSi) or SSI distributions for a given area (Area SSI, e.g. the Mediterranean Sea) and time period (e.g. a winter season or storm climatology over 30 years). In addition, series of SSI distributions can be calculated using a time step (e.g. every year/month over the entire chosen period).

The level of wind speed above which an impact is expected can be indicated using a wind speed threshold value. For this threshold, percentiles (e.g. P98 with minimum value) can be selected that have been calculated for the entire data source and consist of threshold values for each location (grid-cell). Or alternatively, a fixed wind speed threshold value can be given.

4.3.2 Principal scientific results

The Storm Severity Index (SSI) method is based on hourly 10m neutral wind speed data of ERA5 (ECMWF Reanalysis v5) produced by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S). ERA5 consists of reanalysis data where model data (e.g. ocean wave model) is combined with observations into a complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. The current SSI service is limited to the Mediterranean Sea (0.5 x 0.5 deg with 1 x 1 deg uncertainty) for time period 1 January 1979 till 31 December 2020. Other seas can be added after downloading the ERA5 data and calculating corresponding percentiles.

The Storm Severity Index (SSI) method is accessible via the MEI Generator. Alternatively, a notebook is available to perform SSI calculations.

With the MEI generator or notebook a user selects the data source first (currently limited to Med Sea data only) followed by the area of interest, time period, time step and wind speed threshold to start the SSI calculation. SSI calculations can be performed for different purposes. For example, when a user is only interested in a specific storm the SSI can be calculated for the area of the storm track and time duration of the storm. This is called an event SSI calculation or ESSi. Different ESSi can be calculated and compared. However, if a user is interested in the storm severity for a particular area over a specific time period like the winter season, an area SSI or ASSi can be calculated. Both ESSi and ASSi calculations can apply time stepping to create series of SSI calculations. Using time stepping it is possible to calculate, for example, the annual SSI of an area over 40 years.

The wind speed threshold of the SSI calculation (1) specifies to wind speed level above which impact is expected ($SSI > 0$). The calculated percentiles of the data source (P90, P95, P98 and P99) can be selected as wind speed threshold or an absolute fixed threshold value can be applied.

Percentiles have been calculated for each grid cell and represents the wind speed level of the highest 10% (P90), 5% (P95), 2% (P98) and 1% (P99) of wind speed values for the time span of data source (e.g. 40 years). This gives higher threshold values for grid cells in more windy areas. Windspeed values above the threshold are regarded exceptional and therefore causing impact.

The SSI calculation of an event or areas of interest is performed by calculating the daily SSI grid data from the hourly data source (ERA5) data first (1). This daily SSI grid data is subsequently aggregated over SSI specified time steps of time interval and area of interest (2).

$$SSI_{k,day} = \sum_{t=1}^{T=24h} [(\max(0, \frac{v_{k,t}}{v_{threshold}} - 1)^3] \quad (1)$$

k is a single grid cell.

$$SSI_{j,step} = \sum_{t=1}^{Stepsize} SSI_{j,day} \quad (2)$$

j is a single grid cell of the selected area, stepsize is the specified time step (in days)

In addition to calculated SSI grid-cell data per time step for the selected area, time series data of SSI total of the entire area are calculated. The temporal aggregation (hour to time step) will not affect the SSI uncertainty of a grid cell. Spatial aggregation (area totals) is even expected to decrease the relative uncertainty.

Besides the SSI calculation, additional SSI statistical data are calculated for each grid cell and the total area. This data consists of *SSI_{max}*: the maximum (daily) SSI value calculated; *SSI_{rate}*: the average SSI value (zero values excluded) and *SSI_{day}*: number of days the SSI value is greater than zero.

Examples: the calculated SSI map of two medicanes: Numa (13 Nov 2013) and Zorbas (28 Sep 2018) is given in figure 12.

Figure 12 SSI map of Numa and Zorbas (medicanes, med. cyclone)

Another example, the calculated annual SSI time series over 40 years for the Mediterranean Sea is given in figure 13 together with the SSI map of 1981 2001 and 2019.

Figure 13 Annual SSI time series for the Med. Sea and SSI maps of 1981, 2001 and 2019

4.3.3 Blue Cloud added value

The Storm Severity Index (SSI) service offers scientific users of Blue Cloud the ability to quantify the severity of storm events. Using percentiles or absolute values for wind speed threshold the severity can be related to specific impact. For impact such as coastal damage percentile 98 is typically used as wind speed threshold. Other impact such as Eddy killing (sea circulation) might require an absolute wind speed threshold value. The user can decide what wind speed threshold suits best the impact quantification of severe storms (SSI) given a specific sea, ocean or coastal phenomena.

In addition, the SSI service can be used to investigate the storm severity (i.e. impact) for a specific area like the Mediterranean Sea over a period of time such as the winter season. Also the trend of storm severity over a long time period such as 40 years can be investigated using time steps (e.g.

annual time stepping). The annual SSI over 40 years can be useful to investigate the storm severity trend given climate change in that area.

4.4 Simple access to carbon data

4.4.1 Short description of the service

The service provides information on how to search for and retrieve subsets of inorganic carbon data without having to download the full file(s) by using a data server largely used by the oceanographic community.

The data server ERDDAP, developed by the NOAA, allows users to explore, select and download subsets of data, in their preferred format, regardless of the format of origin. It standardizes the variable names and units of position (latitude, longitude, altitude/depth) and time. It can be accessed via script and removes the need of downloading ("copy" or "replicate" in Blue-Cloud) multiple and/or large files that may or may not be of interest to the user. Any kind of data can be used either gridded (as model data) or discrete (as *in situ* data). Many marine research data holders currently have ERDDAP servers; some examples in Europe are EMODnet, IFREMER, ICOS, EMSO, the Irish Marine Institute, the British Oceanographic Data Center (BODC).

4.4.2 Blue Cloud added value

Many inorganic carbon data repositories run public facing APIs for access to their data they are rarely used and other people tend to use more traditional data access techniques. Federating these disparate repositories into a single endpoint, and integrating that endpoint into a VRE arena, is an important step forward in enabling these data to be utilised effectively with the latest research tools and techniques. This integration effort also signals to the data repositories the increasing importance of services such as Blue-Cloud as a channel for disseminating their data and the usefulness of their output to an ever-widening audience.

5 Demonstrator # 4 – Fish, a matter of scales

The FisheriesAtlas is a unique global collaboration to harmonise, standardise, and maintain public global fisheries datasets. It will continue to provide the largest global collection of shared fisheries data under the FIRMS governance leadership.

GRSF is an interactive web-based system that assigns unique identifiers to stocks and fisheries for an improved and comprehensive stock status data coverage, in support to the monitoring of the status and trends of all fishery resources. GRSF also aims to support the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) Indicator 14.4.1 “Proportion of fish stocks within biologically sustainable levels”, and a tool for traceability and eco-labelling schemes with the aim to connect seafood industries and consumers to scientific evidence of the status of stocks and fisheries.

There are a variety of VRE’s available for end-users, while others are used for developing and testing. The Global Tuna Atlas is released as a public tool in the FAO website, while the GRSF unique identifiers are now being field tested in a traceability project of UNDP. Other uses of the VRE technology include two training VRE’s of FAO with already 800+ exposed trainees, and the further development of the regional database concept where R-tools now can upload, validate and harmonise fisheries datasets in an organised workflow to the spatial data infrastructure.

5.1 Fisheries atlas

5.1.1 Short description of the service

The service delivers an online **fisheries atlas** of EU waters and beyond, providing harmonised time-series of catch, commodities and trade data. The atlas is an expansion of the FAO Tuna Atlas, it is scalable and flexible and offers features for data analysis to compute indicators, statistics, interactive maps, etc (Figure 14).

The service makes fisheries data accessible through a map Viewer, ISO/OGC metadata and data services, analytical and reporting tools and R Shiny, Jupyter and Markdown reporting services.

Figure 14 A web snapshot of the fisheries atlas

The objective is to have this service open and public, where possible. All software and components of the service are open source and can be used in other contexts. Fisheries data are often very

specific and require a management part, as on the harmonisation of fisheries catch data, where FAO and IRD collaborate. Data will be published only after the legal owners or custodians approve them.

5.1.2 Principal scientific results

The activity resulted in the release of the FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas is also accessible through the website of FAO: www.fao.org/fishery/geoserver/tunaatlas/

The FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas (GTA) builds on historical atlases, which were merged in 2019 into one coordinated initiative under governance responsibility of the FIRMS partnership. All currently available information is provided by the five tuna Regional Fishery Management Organizations (CCSBT, ICCAT, IATTC, IOTC, WCPFC/SPC). The Atlas facilitates access to authoritative, spatialized - 5° or 1° squares - and standardized public data on tuna fisheries, offering a comprehensive overview of the catches of about 50 tuna and tuna-like species by industrial – period from 1950 to 2019 – and, increasingly, artisanal fisheries. Also, data for 100 bycatch species including several species of pelagic sharks are added.

A new workflow-module (Figure 15) was recently added to upload predefined data-sets and harmonise data for more generic fisheries. This evolution will enable the establishment of regional databases and atlases, delivering statistical data management capacity to where it is most needed, i.e. in resource-poor organisations. These can now benefit from cost-effective EU-Infrastructure delivered cloud-services.

Figure 15 Presentation of the new workflow of the FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas

5.1.3 Blue Cloud added value

Blue Cloud services enable collaboration across the globe on complex fisheries data, collected with similar, but ever so subtle different objectives. Harmonising and standardising these data require very interactive processes across different data providers and analysts. Blue Cloud provides easy access to the data and contributes to a transparent fisheries data elaboration and analysis.

5.2 Global record of stocks and fisheries (GRSF)

5.2.1 Short description of the service

The objective of the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF) is to deliver a scalable and robust open data portal for fisheries data in EU waters and beyond, with a focus on assessment status and management of natural living resources. The service expands the existing GRSF VRE with new information for approved status assessments of fisheries, including those from other sources and demonstrators. The GRSF contains Unique Identifiers of Stocks and Fisheries and the descriptions of the area and management structure. It is thus a natural companion of the Fisheries Atlas (service described above) that has more catch location specific information.

This process is not open access, but private since the information needs to be first aligned and validated. The prime purpose of the service is to develop a public dataset using Blue Cloud services for harmonization, standardization, maintenance and publication of fisheries data from different sources.

5.2.2 Principal scientific results

The GRSF (Figure 16) was conceived to provide a public source of information synthesised from 3 separate but overlapping information sources from government (FAO - FIRMS partnership), academia (University of Washington) and private sector (Sustainable Fisheries Partnership, USA). These organisations provided in-kind contributions as data, know-how and data integration effort to merge data. The collaboration greatly improved on data interoperability by aligning subject vocabularies and descriptions. GRSF is used to generate unique identifiers on stocks and fisheries. It now contains validated information on species distribution (including maps), management authority and structure, and ancillary information. Ancillary information can be flexible, thanks to the semantic knowledge base, and range from capture time series to information if the stock is used for SDG assessment.

The objective to develop a coherent view over global stocks and fisheries was achieved. The usefulness of the GRSF is further evidenced through the use of its record in a UNDP challenge on fish traceability, where GRSF identifiers will be used to inform the entire value-chain from “catch to cook” on the provenance, sustainability and management of the fish.

The resulting services can be accessed online:

- Catalogue <https://i-marine.d4science.org/web/grsf/data-catalogue>
- Map Viewer <https://i-marine.d4science.org/web/grsf/map-viewer>

Web services and competency queries: on request

Figure 16 A web snapshot of the fisheries atlas

5.2.3 Blue Cloud added value

GRSF successfully defragmented global fisheries related information. A truly global information source with geospatial explicit data from authoritative sources can significantly improve claims on sustainability and reduce the costs of data management in the value-chain. GRSF provides the missing link between provenance and product information and improves reliability and timeliness of fisheries traceability information.

6 Demonstrator #5 – aquaculture monitoring

The aquaculture monitor can become an important information source for local and national governments that lack the capacity to implement a national detection and / or remote sensing based monitoring tool. It can thus provide a monitor for several Sustainable Development Goals such as 14 "Life below water", and 2 "Food Security".

There are no customers yet for this demonstrator as the service is not yet open to users external to the Blue-Cloud consortium.

6.1 Aquaculture cage detection

6.1.1 Short description of the service

The combined use of Earth Observation (EO) images and GIS (Geographic Information Systems) is a mature practice for the global management of aquaculture. The access to Earth Observation images has become more reliable, with always higher resolution and precision and more frequent revisits. Satellite EO –Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2- is of great potential to monitor the global aquaculture in term of spatial planning, seasonal activities, impact of climate change.

6.1.2 Principal scientific results

The objectives of the demonstrator were to:

1. Implement a cage detection algorithm based on S1 data;
2. Test if cage activity can be monitored using high-resolution data;
3. Integrate results in a VRE, and align with georeferenced farm characteristics.

The first objective was met and the results can be consulted in the VRE (see links below, Figures 17 & 18). The second objective was tested over a difficult area with optical high-resolution imagery shared through FAO by Planet.com. It required that at least 3 images over a grow-out season to be acquired and compared to identify cages that were active. Due to persistent cloud-cover it proved impractical to develop a re-applicable service, and results of the monitoring service could not be validated.

The jupyter notebook developed by CLS for cage detection using S1 is deployed on the D4Science infrastructure, and the outputs in the form of a geopackage are easily integrated in GeoNetwork of the demonstrator.

The results can be accessed here:

1. on Geonetwork: [aquaculture farm detection](#)
2. on OpenFairViewer:
 - a. embedded in VRE [blue-cloud aquacultureatlasgeneration/viewer](#)
 - b. direct link: <https://aquaculturemonitor.d4science.org/aquaculturemonitor-viewer/>

Figure 17 A web snapshot of the aquaculture atlas

Figure 18 VRE access screen to the aquaculture maps

6.1.3 Blue Cloud added value

This Demonstrator evidences how an infrastructure approach results in a scalable and replicable service that improves the re-usability and reduces costs of generating aquaculture maps. The VRE allows managing users and access, and at the same time allows access to different types of geospatial explicit data to visualise aquaculture in the wider context. The resulting maps can be enriched with other data from the infrastructure, such as geolocated information on farms (e.g. species farmed), and can be used to extract geo-statistics (e.g. coverage by cages and species).

6.2 Coastal pond detection and land classification

6.2.1 Short description of the service

The service has been developed to distinguish between permanent ponds and season rice-fields (sawah) in southern Sulawesi. It uses an AI random forest approach to classify land-types in coastal areas. The first areas to test the service were selected with FAO who is interested in the correct identification of coastal aquaculture in the tropics. The service combines a data analysis with data such as georeferenced local statistics.

6.2.2 Principal scientific results

This service demonstrated that AI land-classification can be applied to new areas and land-use classes, including complex peri-urban and coastal areas in tropical countries. The validation, done with local expertise, showed that AI products can be co-designed to meet local needs, and that results can be shared through a VRE.

Figure 19 An AI generated view over the ROI; South Sulawesi and the classifiers

The above map (Figure 19) is the result of an AI analysis over the Maros area in South-Sulawesi, and takes sentinel 2 images as input. The generated land-classification is detailed on the right distinguishing land and water areas of different types.

6.2.3 Blue Cloud added value

The objective was to evidence the usefulness, reliability and precision of AI derived maps over complex land-use systems. The Blue Cloud can provide the resources needed to continue this development through different areas over the world. For this specific described area, the focus is now on developing the service and validating the results in a collaboration with a local institute.

7 Conclusion

The 12 thematic marine services described made extensive use of the Blue-Cloud framework and its rich set of resources. They illustrate well the large span and interesting subjects that can be developed using such resources, from genomics to wildlife as well as environmental data coming from multiple disciplines and repositories. They all together demonstrate Blue-Cloud's potential in different fields of marine research, ranging from biodiversity to environmental science, as well as fisheries and aquaculture.

The Blue-Cloud Open Science Platform allows:

- Reducing the running time of algorithms by using parallel computing
- Machine learning approaches, i.e. new types of statistical perspective when analysing ocean data
- Large storage of heavy datasets thanks to the high number of cores and RAM available
- Usage of multiple and interdisciplinary data sources of heavy computing cost
- Non programming experts to reuse and reproduce the methods using the notebooks developed by experts

And therefore:

- Facilitates the use of different Blue Data Infrastructures and then of various datasets and parameters
- Allows researchers, students and academics to explore the data further, for a better understanding of the services proposed.
- Enables collaboration across the globe on complex data and different objectives.

The overall conclusion is that the initial Blue Cloud framework already proved to be a great pilot that will be further enhanced and expanded in the next step through the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.